

Complex Compounds of Substituted Thioureas. Part V. Silver Derivatives of Mono- and Di-*N*-acetyl- and -phenylthioureas and Mercury(II) Derivatives of *N*-Acetylthiourea and Di-*N*-phenylthiourea

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Several complex compounds of mono- and di-*N*-acetylthioureas and mono- and di-*N*-phenylthioureas with silver salts and a few of *N*-acetylthiourea and di-*N*-phenylthiourea with mercury salts have been prepared and their properties studied. The constitution of these compounds has been discussed.

Many solid addition compounds of silver salts with thiourea have been reported in the literature, where silver ion shows a diversity of co-ordination number. As in the case of copper¹, these can also be classified into six groups, viz. (1:7)², (1:5), (1:3), (1:2.5), (1:2), and (1:1)³.

Only compounds between silver salt and substituted thiourea, so far reported, are (Ag. 4 etu)NO₃, (Ag₂.3 etu)(NO₃)₂, (Ag₂.3 etu)S₂O₃, (Ag. 3 etu)Cl, (Ag. 2 etu)Br, (Ag. etu)I, and (Ag. etu)₂O (where 'etu' is ethylenethiourea) by Morgan and Burstall⁴ and Lal and Krall⁵, where, in some cases, fractional molecules of the ligand per metal ion are also present.

In the present investigation on the formation of solid complexes between mono- and di-*N*-acetylthioureas and mono- and di-*N*-phenylthioureas with different silver salts, five solid compounds, viz., AgNO₃.AcTh, AgNO₃.2AcTh, 2AgNO₃.5 AcTh, AgNO₃.Ac₂Th, and AgNO₃.Ph₂Th, have been reported for the first time and the compound, AgNO₃.PhTh, prepared previously by Lal and Krall⁵, has been obtained under different experimental conditions.

In continuation of our work⁶ on mercury-substituted thiourea complexes, an analogous study has been made in the present communication, using *N*-acetylthiourea and di-*N*-phenylthiourea as co-ordinating ligands, when compounds Hg(NO₃)₂.AcTh, HgAc₂.AcTh, and HgCl₂.Ph₂Th have been prepared, besides HgCl₂.AcTh and HgCl₂.2AcTh, reported previously⁶.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mono- and di-*N*-acetylthiourea and mono- and di-*N*-phenylthioureas were prepared by the methods described in earlier parts of this series^{1,7,8}.

1. Part I, Siddhanta and Banerjee, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 747.
2. Lauter and Stauff, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1937, **26**, 724.
3. Beilstein, *Org. Chem.*, Band III, Syst. 216, p. 186.
4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 143.
5. This *Journal*, 1937, **14**, 474.
6. Part II, Siddhanta and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1951, **38**, 765.
7. Part III, Banerjee and Sukthankar, this *Journal*, 1962, **39**, 107.
8. Part IV, *idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, **40**, 367.

Silver Derivatives of Substituted Thiourcas

Uni-(N-acetylthiourea)-silver Nitrate.—An aqueous solution of silver nitrate (25 ml, 4 g.) was added slowly to that of *N*-acetylthiourea (175 ml, 3 g.) at room temperature, when a white compound was formed which gradually changed to black in presence of light. On keeping the mixture for about 10 mins., it was filtered, washed successively with small amounts of water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed; yield 3 g. (4.4%). (Found: Ag, 37.28, 37.39; N, 14.46, 14.39; S, 11.02, 10.95. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires Ag, 37.47; N, 14.58; S, 11.11%.)

The same compound was formed between solutions of silver nitrate (25 ml, 4.5 g.) and *N*-acetylthiourea (200 ml, 1.5 g.) at ice-temperature (30 mins.); yield 2.5 g. (67%). (Found: Ag, 37.30, 37.42; S, 11.24, 11.06%.)

The compound does not react with cold or hot dilute HCl, but dilute NaOH solution decomposes it with the formation of a black residue. It is slightly soluble in water but insoluble in ethanol, acetone, and chloroform.

Bis-(N-acetylthiourea)-silver Nitrate.—An aqueous solution of silver nitrate (25 ml, 2 g.) was added slowly with stirring to that of *N*-acetylthiourea (250 ml, 3 g.), when a white shining crystalline compound was formed, which slightly changed to grey in presence of light. The mixture was kept for about 15 minutes with occasional stirring. It was filtered, and washed with minimum quantity of water and then with ethanol. It was dried in air and analysed; yield 3.7 g. (77%). (Found: Ag, 26.45, 26.56; N, 17.05, 16.96; S, 15.65, 15.72. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires Ag, 26.58; N, 17.24; S, 15.77%.)

The compound does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot acid dissolves it; the solution on cooling forms a white precipitate. With NaOH solution it turns black. The compound is soluble in water or ethanol, sparingly soluble in acetone, but insoluble in chloroform. It melts at 153°.

Pentakis-(N-acetylthiourea)-di-silver Nitrate.—An ice-cold aqueous solution (450 ml) of *N*-acetylthiourea (6 g.) was acidified with 2*N*-HNO₃ (10 ml). To this solution was added slowly with stirring an ice-cold aqueous solution (25 ml) of AgNO₃ (2 g.), when a milk-white precipitate was formed. The mixture was kept at ice-temperature for about 20 mins., filtered, washed successively with cold water and ethanol, dried in vacuum, and analysed. All operations were carried out in darkness. (Found: Ag, 23.43, 23.31; N, 18.14, 18.20; S, 17.29, 17.32. $2\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot 5\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires Ag, 23.20; N, 18.07; S, 17.21%). Definite chemical entity of the compound was confirmed by analysis of the product crystallised from a dilute nitric acid solution.

The compound is white and stable. It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but dissolves in hot acid forming a white crystalline precipitate when cooled. It is decomposed by dilute alkalis, both hot and cold. The substance is insoluble in water or chloroform, but sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone.

Uni-(di-N-acetylthiourea)-silver Nitrate.—A concentrated acetone solution (95%) of silver nitrate (25 ml, 3 g.) was added slowly with stirring to that of di-*N*-acetylthiourea (75 ml, 3 g.), when the colour of the mixture changed from yellow to orange and finally red with simultaneous formation of a black compound. On keeping the mixture for about 15 mins., it was filtered, washed with acetone, and analysed when dry. (Found: Ag, 32.60,

32.79; N, 12.59, 12.88; S, 9.81, 9.71. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNHCOCH}_3$ requires Ag, 32.71; N, 12.73; S, 9.70%.

The compound is black and stable. It does not react with hot or cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, and chloroform.

Uni-(N-phenylthiourea)-silver Nitrate.—An aqueous solution of AgNO_3 (25 ml, 5.5 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an aqueous solution of *N*-phenylthiourea (250 ml, 2 g.), when a milk-white precipitate was formed, which slowly turned brown and finally black. It was filtered after about 20 mins., washed successively with water and acetone, dried in vacuum, and analysed. (Found: Ag, 33.68, 33.59; S, 10.15, 9.98. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2$ requires Ag, 33.53; N, 13.05; S, 9.94%.)

An identical compound was prepared using AgNO_3 (2 g.) and *N*-phenylthiourea (5 g.) in ice-cold, acidified (HNO_3) solution (700 ml). (Found: Ag, 33.72, 33.65; N, 13.16, 13.22; S, 9.97, 10.04%). The same compound, though previously reported by Lal and Kral², has been prepared in different experimental conditions in the present work.

The compound is white but turns black in presence of light. It does not react with cold dilute acid or alkali solutions. It dissolves in hot dilute HCl solution forming a white crystalline compound in the cold. Hot dilute NaOH solution decomposes the compound. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, and chloroform.

Uni-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-silver Nitrate.—An ice-cold solution of AgNO_3 (3 g.) in 50% acetone was added slowly with stirring to an ice-cold solution of di-*N*-phenylthiourea (4.5 g.) in the same medium, when a red solution was formed. On keeping the mixture for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with occasional stirring, the colour gradually discharged and a white compound was formed. This was then filtered, washed with acetone, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Ag, 27.25, 27.18; N, 10.69, 10.72; S, 7.81, 8.12. $\text{AgNO}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCSNH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ requires Ag, 27.11; N, 10.55; S, 8.04%). The same compound was formed between acetone solutions of AgNO_3 (5.5 g.) and di-*N*-phenylthiourea (2 g.) at room temperature (20 mins.). (Found: Ag, 27.20, 27.29; S, 7.91, 8.08%.)

The compound is white but turns grey in presence of light. It does not react with cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, but dissolves in hot acid forming a white crystalline compound in the cold. It is decomposed with hot dilute NaOH solution. The compound insoluble in water or chloroform, but slightly soluble in ethanol or acetone.

Mercury (II) Derivatives

Uni-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercury(II) Nitrate.—The compound was obtained as a black precipitate when an aqueous solution of mercuric nitrate (50 ml, 8 g.) was added slowly to that of *N*-acetylthiourea (300 ml, 5.5 g.) at room temperature. After about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the product was filtered, washed with water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. (Found: Hg, 47.60, 47.48; N, 12.74, 12.81; S, 7.22, 7.23. $\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires Hg, 47.44; N, 12.62; S, 7.21%). The black compound is stable towards cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions, but hot solutions decompose it to a red mass. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, and chloroform.

Uni-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercury(II) Acetate.—Mercuric acetate (8 g.) in water (50 ml) was added slowly with stirring at room temperature to a solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (5.5 g.) in water (250 ml), when a black precipitate was formed. This was filtered

after about 45 mins., and treated as above. (Found: Hg, 46.05, 45.93; N, 6.42, 6.41; S, 7.36, 7.36. $\text{Hg}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHC(SNH}_2)_2$ requires Hg, 45.91; N, 6.41; S, 7.32%). It is black and very stable. It does not react with hot or cold dilute HCl or NaOH solutions. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, and chloroform.

Uni-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercury(II) Chloride.—An aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (100 ml, 7g.) was added at room temperature to an aqueous solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (150 ml, 4g.) when a white precipitate was formed. On keeping for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, the mixture was filtered and treated as above. (Found: Hg, 49.75, 49.60; N, 6.82, 6.79; Cl, 17.35, 17.29. $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHC(SNH}_2)_2$ requires Hg, 49.3; N, 6.88; Cl, 17.4%). The same compound was obtained by Siddhanta and Banerjee⁶ in anhydrous acetone medium at ice-cold temperature.

Bis-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercury(II) Chloride.—A hot aqueous solution of mercuric chloride (50 ml, 2g.) was added slowly with stirring to a boiling aqueous solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (100 ml, 5g.), when a white precipitate was formed. The mixture was then digested on a steam bath for about 20 mins., filtered, and treated as the previous compounds. (Found: Hg, 39.80, 39.90; N, 11.35, 11.42; Cl, 14.25, 14.31. $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{CH}_3\text{CONHC(SNH}_2)_2$ requires Hg, 39.68; N, 11.08; Cl, 14.02%). The same compound was prepared by Siddhanta and Banerjee⁶ at room temperature in aqueous acetone solution.

Uni-(di-N-phenylthiourea)-mercury(II) Chloride.—An absolute ethanolic solution of mercuric chloride (50 ml, 3g.) was added slowly with stirring at room temperature to a solution of di-*N*-phenylthiourea in the same solvent (250 ml, 3.5g.), when a deep yellow compound was precipitated. On keeping the mixture for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, it was filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol, and dried in air. (Found: Hg, 40.32, 40.41; N, 5.58, 5.59; Cl, 14.34, 14.27. $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHC(SNHC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ requires Hg, 40.14; N, 5.60; Cl, 14.19%). The compound is deep yellow in colour and stable. It does not react with cold or hot dilute HCl, but hot dilute alkali solution decomposes it, forming a black mercuric sulphide. It is insoluble in water, ethanol or chloroform, and sparingly soluble in acetone.

DISCUSSION

Similar to thiourea-mercuric complexes⁶, tetra-co-ordination of silver attributes a stable xenon structure to it. It is, however, strange that like copper-thiourea complex, with silver salts too, no solid tetra-co-ordinated thiourea complex has yet been reported. In the present investigation, all attempts to prepare compounds in solid state with larger number of ligands, viz., AcTh, Ac₂Th, PhTh or Ph₂Th, per silver ion have failed, though such complexes exist with thiourea and ethylenethiourea molecules. It is probable that in these cases, a few of such complexes exist in soluble form. It may, however, be remarked that the tendency for co-ordination of thiourea with silver ion decreases in *N*-substituted thioureas. As an analogy with *N*-substituted thiourea-copper complexes⁶, *N*-phenylthioureas show lesser co-ordinating capacity to silver ion than *N*-acetylthioureas. Similar to copper and mercury salts⁶, besides solid mononuclear silver salt, many stable polynuclear derivatives containing even fractional molecules of thio-base per metal ion are reported to exist (including one reported in the present paper), and these can as well be represented using thiourea a bridging molecule through its bivalent sulphur atom⁶.

All mercury compounds reported in this paper are stable, highly insoluble, and do not respond to any test for the anions, viz., chloride, nitrate, or acetate ions, as the case may be, and may be represented as non-electrolytes:

1:2 Type

1:1 Type

(where X represents the anion) where in tetra-co-ordination of mercury, thus attaining a stable Radon configuration, is manifested.

Sincere thanks of the authors are due to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta, Section of Geochemistry, for his interest, to Prof. G. M. Nabar, Director, University Department of Chemical Technology, Bombay, and to Prof. S. K. Bhattacharyya, Head of the Department of Applied Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, for providing laboratory facilities.

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Received October 20, 1962.